
PROFESSIONAL SKILLS FOR LIS PROFESSIONAL FOR PROVIDING QUALITATIVE LIBRARY SERVICES

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Abstract:

The need for quality skills to provide quality services should be the motto for a professional in rendering services. This paper is presented because of the requirement, quality skills, and importance to a LIS professional. A basic introduction to the job description of a LIS professional includes a detailed description of skills and competencies. Different levels of skills and their effect on the services. User view and professional understanding of the LIS profession are provided in detail with relevant citations and references. Why do we need qualitative services in a library, whether a private or a public library? New generation librarians' tech savviness and use of new and faster tools and techniques. these are qualities that are the need of the hour for a library science professional. It plays a crucial and apt role in understanding and collecting information and disseminating it. Professional skills are meant to provide adequate services to the user community, which is very important and emphasized here. It describes the methodology attributed to studying the essential skills and competencies of a new generation of LIS professionals.

Keywords: Professional Skills, Competencies Skills, Professional Development, Work Skill. Quality Services

Introduction:

Professional skills combine hard and soft skills; they have a broad meaning and a vast depth of understanding in library and information science. A Librarian handles the everyday functions of libraries (whether public or private libraries). User interaction is the main assigned work. To help the library run efficiently and smoothly and to serve the library's users, a specific set of good skills is mandatory. We need to analyse and understand skills and competencies. Skills and Competency- Both are sometimes referred to as synonyms, but in actual

words, both have a slight difference as the core concept of skill and competency objectives differ. A minor difference is discussed below for more understanding.

The library should always provide quality service to retain and develop and increase its importance to the user community and successfully imply the best role of the library in teaching, learning, and research. Quality services mean services which gives a good effect on the user and exceed the expectations and perceptions. A quality of a professional can be attributed to his knowledge to handle the core responsibilities, his

attitude, and his clever way of disseminating the knowledge acquired as a librarian. A LIS professional should be well aware of the past and present and stipulate the future with experience developed. It helps the user community use more library services per library purview. Apart from regular services such as Circulation / Borrowing Cataloguing, Acquisitions / Collection Management, and Course Reserves, Selective dissemination of information, Reference Services, Inter Library Loan Service, Photocopying / Printing Service, Orientation and Information Sessions, Audio Visual Service, Multimedia Section. All of this help professionally qualified LIS personnel to provide qualitative services as LIS professional. Quality service is the need of any service provider now a day.

What Are Professional Skills?

Professional skills are abilities and career competencies used in the workplace and are advantageous for almost every employment. Hard skills and soft skills are combined to form professional talents.

When librarians work at a library, they contribute industry-specific hard talents and transferable soft abilities. Hard skills are profession-specific abilities, such as operating library software or comprehending information categorization. Soft skills may be used in various settings, such as time management, critical thinking, and timeliness. Throughout the workday, librarians employ a range of talents to categorize books, e-resources, films, and other media, organize and enhance the library, and assist patrons in finding information. Hard and soft skills are the two categories of skills that make up professional skills.

Hard Skill: Hard skills are required to do a specific task successfully. These talents frequently change depending on the function you will be doing inside the organization.

Soft Skill: Contrarily, soft skills, which are typically self-taught and self-developed and are valued by all employers regardless of the sort of company they work for, are becoming increasingly important.

Competencies:

Apart from skills, a LIS professional must and should be a very competent person. Competencies are a person's behavioural attitude, smartness, and knowledge; knowing a person's behaviour with the right attitude may lead them to be popular among the users due to their knowledge, professionalism, and positive attitude. It can be an integral part of services and thus ease overall skills; various competencies – including core competencies, which any successful employee requires to rise through an organization.

- To be a motivator who can establish and maintain effective working relationships with associates, supervisors, volunteers, other community agencies, and the public.
- Should have immense knowledge and technical know-how of library service
- Be a good organizer, demonstrate knowledge of library materials and resources
- Creativity to develop and implement library programs and services
- Positive attitude toward library users with special needs
- Accuracy and skill in typing

Professional Skills For LIS Professional For Providing Qualitative Library Services:

Professional skills are a set of specific abilities that a LIS professional needs to perform on his given job and to perform their duties and responsibilities in a disciplined manner. Particular skills are needed for qualitative library services as mentioned below:

Communication:

An essential and highly desired ability is effective communication. Communication skills are a necessary and highly desired power in effective communication. Writing and speaking are both forms of communication. These communications should be used in various formats because they cover many more intricate dimensions and facets. A good librarian should have good resources and an eye for detail. He should also be able to communicate well with others who have opposing agendas or policies. To persuade or influence the target audience to their point of view, librarians need to be skilled at diplomacy and negotiation. They should also be able to speak the "language" of the target audience. Marketing and promotion skills are essential for librarians. They need to be able to market their abilities and expertise. Effective presentation abilities are crucial.

Teamwork:

A good team player, team leader, and ringmaster are all qualities that a librarian should possess, in addition to working well in groups. A librarian should be open to forming new connections outside of the library. They have a close working relationship with IT and other fields. Wherever it is necessary, a librarian must be able to form connections, alliances, and networks with people and organizations. They must be able to collaborate across disciplines and be a team player.

User Focus:

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All librarians should be able to keep up ties with the user base and ensure that new users are added with references from current users or referees. They needed to develop into a more beneficial and equal partnership where the librarian and the user collaborated more equally. A librarian who enjoys interacting with people, values the variety of user experiences, sees things from the user's point of view, and actively uses developing technology to give their users a voice now has the capacity and duty to provide content.

Problem Solving:

The ability to solve problems should be a trait of the librarian. Confusion or issues with the user's research or library could arise. The ability to assess problems, make wise decisions, and solve them is something that the librarian aspires to have.

Initiative:

The librarian or library personnel exhibit initiative by taking charge of circumstances and resolving them independently. Employers can see that you are accepting personal responsibility and growing as a leader by doing this.

Organization:

Most of a librarian's time is spent arranging the library's books, journals, reference materials, CDs/DVDs, electronic resources, periodicals, and newspapers. An organized librarian can update the library's catalogue as new materials are received or a user utilizes the medium. Patience, critical thought, and attention to detail are necessary for the organization.

Cataloguing:

Since organizing information is a daily task for a librarian, cataloguing is an essential ability. A library typically employs software to catalogue its inventory, which can help save time and maintain the library's media collection's organization. The capacity to order items by date, name, or alphabetical order, as

well as the ability to gather information, are all talents that librarians offer to the cataloguing process.

Self-Evaluation of Service:

Professionals working in libraries must be able to assess and analyse the services they offer to the community of users. This method of self-evaluation will aid in comprehending and identifying weak points in the services and result in their modification to better appeal to the user community, ultimately assisting in achieving optimum efficiency and effectiveness.

Attraction of users:

The librarian needs to be able to draw people into the library. Librarians must focus on strategies to attract customers and encourage the most use of the library's information resources and services. The librarian should take advantage of emerging technologies to draw in consumers and provide quick library services.

Learn and use innovative technologies:

This is currently one of the most crucial professional skills for librarians. In addition to all the technological developments, everyday actions produce more data than before. Because librarians have the necessary skills and knowledge to make the most effective use of these vast sources of information, new revolutionary technologies are advantageous to them.

Presentation Skills:

Presenting well is a necessary skill in practically every industry today. Presentation skills would be helpful when library personnel interacted with the student, Teachers, management, publishers, vendors, etc.

Leadership Skills:

Effective leadership is dependent on a variety of critical qualities. Employers place a high value on these abilities because they require interacting with people in a way that inspires, motivates, and fosters respect. Professionals in

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libraries must therefore possess leadership qualities.

Computer Skills:

Since most libraries in today's world use electronic resources, digital records, and online catalogues, librarians must regularly use their computer abilities. This involves using cataloguing software, search engines, digital encyclopaedia, and software designed specifically for libraries. A librarian with more advanced computer abilities could be able to introduce library activities or community outreach workshops that instruct users in using computers.

Customer Services:

Library personnel considers customer service to be a top priority. Beyond learning how to give customers high-quality service, the focus includes observing societal changes and trying to find solutions to new problems that staff members face at work. In addition to how we interact with customers verbally and respond to their needs, customer service also involves how we interact non-verbally and talk about customers when they aren't present.

Creativity Skills

To think creatively is to use your imagination to come up with fresh concepts or approach a subject or issue from a new or different angle. People that are creative thinkers view things from an original perspective that is hidden from others. They can identify patterns and linkages in complicated systems that lead to opportunities. If you have a creative mind, it will help you solve challenging puzzles or develop novel approaches to assignments.

How to Improve Librarian Skills for Qualitative Library Services?

The Librarian or the library staff should improve their professional skills for healthy Library services. Then only

librarians can develop and offer new and essential services at the correct time to correct users.

- Participate in outside training courses or workshops and seminars
- Attending the conferences
- Attend the academic courses and certifications for professionals
- Learn to organize your workplace
- To practice using quick-changing techniques
- To increase staff morale and lower absenteeism
- Understand the user's needs
- Study on innovative technologies
- Internal training program

Conclusion:

They understand the need, use, and implementation of a LIS professional's professional skills for quality service. A librarian has to be qualified with certain qualities as discussed and should have technical and software latest versions knowledge. It helps to better give and decimate his duties aptly and adequately to the user community. Skills can be categorized as Traditional, newly acquired, technical & personality. These skills can make us understand the need for more development s in which area should be focused on by the librarian. Proper analysis and adapt uses of one's skill for professional growth and understanding of the need inside a library which helps to serve the guests or a patron, can be ascertained. A proper habitual cycle of adaptive methods for new and lifelong learning in many fields as and when needed should be kept in mind always and used whenever necessary.

In the present era, all the skills acquired by library professionals should have a quality that helps them to provide good services with their skill sets. Many reiterated that computing skills, library automation, and digitization are essential for LIS professionals in the present scenario. It was found that a well-disciplined, knowledgeable adaptive, team player, well-behaved, Bibliographic service. Optimistic and interpersonal abilities with a good attitude were reportedly essential and needed of the hour in all librarians. These all contribute to the quality of services provided to the user communities.

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